

Thiopegan Derivatives. Part XLIX

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Some 9 : 10-thiopegan derivatives with cyano group in position 2 have been synthesised by the condensation of ethyl anthranilate thiocyanate with α -bromo α -cyano acetophenones, the latter in turn having been obtained by the bromination of α -cyano acetophenones

Although a good deal of work has been carried out on 9 : 10-thiopegan derivatives¹⁻⁵, but no attempt seems to have been made so far to introduce cyano group in any of the positions of thiopegan nucleus. Hence it was considered worthwhile to introduce cyano group in position 2 of the thiopegan nucleus to evaluate their antibacterial properties.

For this purpose, we started with α -bromo acetophenones I which upon treatment with potassium cyanide II gave rise to α -cyano acetophenones III. III in turn were converted into α -bromo α -cyano acetophenones IV by treatment with bromine in the presence of pyridine using chloroform as solvent. The α -bromo α -cyano acetophenones IV thus obtained, upon condensation with ethyl anthranilate thiocyanate V furnished the 9 : 10-thiopegan derivatives VIII with cyano group in position 2, through the probable formation of ethyl anthranilate hydrobromide VI and α -cyano α -thiocyano acetophenones VII.

In fact, the reaction could proceed in a different way also to give IX but the possibility of formation of IX has been ruled out on the basis of presence of I.R. absorption band of $-\text{C} \equiv \text{N}$ group at $2240\text{--}2210\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which is absent in structure IX.

1. D. S. Bariana, H. S. Sachdev and K. S. Narang, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **32**, 644.
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3. H. S. Sachdev, K. S. Dhami and K. S. Narang, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1960, **19C**, 11.
4. H. S. Sachdev and N. K. Ralhan, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1960, **19C**, 109.
5. H. Singh and K. S. Narang, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **40**, 545.

Also the absence of absorption band for keto group at 1690–1720 cm^{-1} rules out the possibility of structure IX. Moreover the product does not form DNP which gives further support to structure VIII.

The N.M.R. spectra of VIII ($R = \text{CH}_3$, $\text{Ar} = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$) run in CDCl_3 exhibited signals at δ 2.1 for CH_3 protons attached to aromatic nucleus (s, 3H), the aromatic protons formed a multiplet at δ 6.90–7.50 (m, 8H) supporting the proposed structure VIII.

EXPERIMENTAL

α -Cyanoacetophenone: A solution of potassium cyanide (20 g.) in water (60 ml.) was added to a solution of α -bromo acetophenone (20 g.) in alcohol (60 ml.) at 30° and the temperature was gradually raised to 50° . The reaction mixture was kept at this temperature for 40 minutes. After cooling, the contents were poured into ice cold water (500 ml.) and filtered. The filtrate was acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid when α -cyano acetophenone separated out. It was collected under suction and crystallised from hot water as brown leaflets, m.p. $80\text{--}81^\circ$.⁶

Other *p*-substituted α -cyano acetophenones were also prepared under identical conditions. Their data is tabulated in Table I.

TABLE I

α -Cyano acetophenones

α -Cyano acetophenone formed	Solvent of crystallisation	Yield%	m.p. $^\circ\text{C}$	Molecular formula	Analytical results	
					Found %	Required %
<i>p</i> -Bromo- α -cyano acetophenone.	Water	75	158	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{BrNO}$	N, 6.40	6.25
<i>p</i> -Chloro- α -cyano acetophenone.	Dil. acetic acid	80	128	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{ClNO}$	N, 7.60	7.79
<i>p</i> -Methyl- α -cyano acetophenone.	Water	56	102	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{NO}$	C, 75.40	75.47
					H, 5.84	5.65
					N, 8.88	8.80
<i>p</i> -Methoxy- α -cyano acetophenone.	Water	62	126	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{NO}_2$	N, 8.28	8.00

α -Bromo α -cyano acetophenone: Pyridine (3.9 g., 0.05 mole) was added to α -cyano acetophenone (7.25 g., 0.05 mole) dissolved in chloroform (75 ml.) and the mixture warmed to 45° . To this was added bromine (8.0 g., 0.05 mole) dissolved in chloroform (10 ml.) during 2 hrs. The contents were kept as such at room temperature overnight and subsequently the chloroform was distilled off under reduced pressure. The residue was washed with water several times to remove pyridine hydrobromide and finally extracted with ether.

The ether extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the solvent was distilled off. Finally α -bromo α -cyano acetophenone was collected at 135–140°/8 mm; the yield being 7.20 g. (64%).

Other *p*-substituted α -bromo α -cyano acetophenones were also prepared by the overlined procedure except that after the distillation of chloroform, the residue after washing with water gave a solid product in each case, which was crystallised from some suitable solvent. Their data is tabulated in Table II.

TABLE II

 α -Bromo α -cyano acetophenones

α -Bromo α -cyano acetophenone formed	Solvent of crystallisation	Yield%	m.p. °C	M.F.	Analytical results	
					Found %	Required %
α -Bromo α -cyano acetophenone.	—	64	133-140°/8 mm	C ₉ H ₆ BrNO	N, 6.42	6.25
<i>p</i> - α -Dibromo α -cyano acetophenone.	Dil. acetic acid	77	118	C ₉ H ₅ Br ₂ NO	N, 4.70	4.62
<i>p</i> -Chloro- α -bromo α -cyano acetophenone.	-do-	82	103	C ₉ H ₅ BrClNO	N, 5.76	5.41
<i>p</i> -Methyl- α -bromo α -cyano acetophenone.	carbon tetrachloride	75	98	C ₁₀ H ₈ BrNO	C, 50.01 H, 3.62 N, 6.32	50.42 3.36 5.88
<i>p</i> -Methoxy- α -bromo- α -cyano acetophenone.	-do-	81	101	C ₁₀ H ₈ BrNO ₂	N, 5.68	5.51

Synthesis of 2-cyano-3-phenyl 9 : 10-thiopega 2 : 10-diene-4-one: Ethyl anthranilate thiocyanate (2.24 g.) was dissolved in absolute alcohol (10 ml.). To this was added α -bromo α -cyano acetophenone (2.24 g.) dissolved in 10 ml. of the same solvent at room temperature. An exothermic reaction took place followed by the separation of a solid. The reaction mixture was refluxed on a steam bath for 4 hrs. cooled and the precipitate filtered off under suction. The mother liquor was concentrated when a further quantity of a solid separated out. Both the former and the latter solids were crystallised separately from carbon tetrachloride as white needles. They were established to be identical as confirmed by their m.p. and m.m.p. 154° and identical R_f values. The yield on the combined basis was 2.50 g. (70%).

Other *p*-substituted α -bromo α -cyano acetophenones were condensed with ethyl anthranilate thiocyanate and 5-methyl ethyl anthranilate thiocyanate under similar conditions. Their data is tabulated in Table III.

TABLE III

2-Cyano 9 : 10-thiopega-2 : 10-diene-4-one derivatives VIII

Cyano ketone used	R = Ar =		Yield %	m.p. °C	M.F.	Analytical results		
						Found %	Required %	
α -Bromo- α -cyano acetophenone.	H	C ₆ H ₅	70	154	C ₁₇ H ₉ N ₃ OS	C	66.89	67.33
						H	3.46	2.97
						N	13.37	13.86
<i>p</i> - α -dibromo α -cyano acetophenone.	H	-C ₆ H ₄ Br- <i>p</i>	76	164	C ₁₇ H ₈ BrN ₃ OS	N	11.48	10.99
						S	8.53	8.38
<i>p</i> -Chloro α -bromo- α -cyano acetophenone.	H	-C ₆ H ₄ Cl- <i>p</i>	78	192	C ₁₇ H ₈ ClN ₃ OS	N	12.47	12.44
<i>p</i> -Methyl- α -bromo- α -cyano acetophenone.	H	-C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ - <i>p</i>	71	140	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ N ₃ OS	N	13.38	13.25
						S	10.21	10.09
<i>p</i> -Methoxy- α -bromo- α -cyano acetophenone.	H	-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃ - <i>p</i>	82	175	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂ S	N	12.55	12.61
α -Bromo- α -cyano acetophenone.	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	65	174	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ N ₃ OS	N	12.85	13.25
<i>p</i> -Dibromo- α -cyano acetophenone.	CH ₃	-C ₆ H ₄ Br- <i>p</i>	68	167	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ BrN ₃ OS	N	10.24	10.61
<i>p</i> -Chloro- α -bromo- α -cyano acetophenone.	CH ₃	-C ₆ H ₅ Cl- <i>p</i>	61	163	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ ClN ₃ OS	N	11.50	11.92
<i>p</i> -Methyl- α -bromo- α -cyano acetophenone.	CH ₃	-C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ - <i>p</i>	55	158	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ N ₃ OS	N	12.40	12.69
<i>p</i> -Methoxy- α -bromo- α -cyano acetophenone.	CH ₃	-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃ - <i>p</i>	53	156	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂ S	N	11.83	12.10

All these compounds were crystallised from carbon tetrachloride.

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